

The Galaxy Luminosity Function via Clustering Based Redshift Inference: can we find the bottom of the galaxy population?

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Even at low redshifts, observing faint galaxies is a challenge as both deep and wide surveys are needed [1]. In addition to being hard to observe these galaxies are hard to simulate at the same time, as they require very low resolution limits. As faint galaxies are particularly sensitive to dark and baryonic matter coupling and feedback, the faint end of the galaxy luminosity function (GLF) has been in the focus of multiple controversies, including the missing satellite problem or the core-cusp problem .

In this study we use clustering based redshift inference (cluster- z s) to map the $z \sim 0$ GLF down to the faintest possible luminosities, beyond the reach of spectroscopic and photometric redshift surveys.

Clustering based redshift inference

Clustering based redshift inference is a method to derive the redshift distribution of a target dataset statistically. This process exploits the fact that galaxies are clustered (rather than randomly distributed) to derive redshift information for our target sample, using only their observed positions on the sky. The basic idea behind the calculation of cluster- z s is that the spatial distribution of galaxies on the sky is unique at each redshift. This leads to the principle that if two populations of objects overlap on the sky, but are at different redshifts their angular correlation is expected to be zero (ignoring gravitational lensing effects) [see 2]. By calculating the cross-correlation amplitude between the target and the reference dataset in a number of redshift bins it is possible to derive the redshift distribution of the target sample. We follow a similar cluster- z formalism as laid out by [3].

For the calculation there are three samples needed. One dataset consisting of objects with unknown redshifts but known spatial positions for which the cluster- z s are

going to be calculated for. In order to trace the large scale structure a reference set with objects of accurate measurements of their full 3D positions is needed in addition. As the calculated clustering amplitude have to show if objects at a specific redshift are clustered stronger or less, than a uniform population would do, we need an unclustered random dataset to compare to. All of these datasets obviously have to cover the same area on the sky.

The overall process of deriving cluster- z s is explained in greater detail in [4] and is illustrated here for three redshift slices for the ~ 60 square degrees GAMA region G12 in Figure 1. In the left panel the target data-points overlay the reference data-points of three different redshift slices. Secondly the corresponding cross- (w_{tr} , between the target and reference set) and auto-correlation (w_{rr} , between the reference and random set) functions are calculated based on the datasets in the first panel. The cluster- z amplitude is calculated as the integral of w_{tr} and w_{rr} within the clustering ranges shown in the middle panel. If this value is calculated for all redshift slices, the final cluster- z distribution can be constructed.

The faint end of the GLF

Since cluster- z s only consider angular position, we are limited by the depth of the photometric catalogue at $m_r < 22.5$, which is ~ 3 magnitudes beyond the GAMA spectroscopic redshift limit. For this experiment we use positions and total r -band magnitude from the GAMA produced photometric catalogues [5], which are derived from KiDS r -band imaging [6] for the three equatorial GAMA fields. We bin our target sample by observed magnitude, and perform the cluster- z calculation (illustrated in Figure 1) to determine the conditional redshift

Figure 1: Illustration of the clustering redshifts process in one of the equatorial GAMA fields (G12). In the left panel the contours of three different redshift slices at $z = 0.09$ (red), 0.19 (blue), 0.29 (green) with $\Delta z = 0.02$ is shown, on top of a sub-sample of the target data (black). The differences of the cosmic web at these redshifts are used to calculate the cross-correlation of the target dataset and the reference data at these redshifts. By using the integrated results of the resulting cross-correlation function w_{tr} and the auto-correlation function w_{rr} over the corresponding clustering ranges r_c (shown in the middle), the $P_{m,z}$ at these redshifts are calculated. In the last panel the resulting $P_{m,z}$ is shown and the points derived at the three redshift slices are marked accordingly. (reproduced from [4])

distribution $P(z|m)$ for each magnitude bin. For the calculation we are restricted to $z \lesssim 0.5$, as the maximal extent of our GAMA spec- z reference sample. The main technical challenge in our experiment arises from the fact that output of the process of clustering redshift inference is proportional to the redshift distribution for the target sample, up to some unknown scalar. Our strategy is to use a simple parametric model for the evolving GLF to constrain the values for the normalisation factors as it is described in [4].

Our main result of mapping the field GLF at $z \sim 0$ across 14 magnitudes or 5.5 decades in luminosity is shown in Figure 2. The measured slope of the GLF remains remarkably flat over the range $-20 \lesssim M_r \lesssim 13$, with a sharp upturn below $M_r \sim -12.5$ or $\log L/L_\odot \sim 6.5$. A similar upturn has been found for the Coma Cluster by Yamanoi [7]. Following Yamanoi [7], we use a simple model to predict the luminosity function for the Globular Cluster (GC) population, based on our GLF fits. As it is shown in Figure 2 this simple prediction with no free parameters provides a good explanation to our measurements.

Figure 2: Comparison of the resulting GLF measurements (orange) with the literature and the GLF and GCLF models (black). The values $M_r > -10.7$ (grey area) are below our magnitude limits and potentially incomplete. At magnitudes $M_r \gtrsim -11.5$ the GCLF is resulting in larger values than the GLF model. This upturn occurs at the same range where the GCLF is overtaking the GLF, which indicates that at $M_r \gtrsim -11.5$ sub-galactic objects become more numerous than galaxies (reproduced from [4]).

The dominant source of systematic error/uncertainty in our results is the unknown evolution of the mean bias of the target samples over the $0 < z \lesssim 0.5$ interval. Being mindful of these issues, we have focused particularly on the $z \sim 0$ GLF, where the impact of these uncertainties is minimised.

Figure 2 shows that we have mapped the $z \sim 0$ GLF from the most luminous galaxies all the way down to where sub-galactic objects take over as the most numerous extragalactic population.

In doing so we demonstrated the potential for clustering based redshift inference in deriving the GLF. This technique offers manifold applications as it is not limited to the optical only and can be extended: e.g. by using deeper reference sets, or by combining different reference sets even deeper studies would be possible.

References

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Short CV

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